

Impact of Educational Interventions on Menstrual Hygiene Practices: A Comprehensive Study

Dr. S. Vijayamalar ✉

Prof., Head of the Department of Community Health Nursing,
Smt. Nagarathnamma College of Nursing, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Prof. Devinanjappan

Principal, Smt. Nagarathnamma College of Nursing, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Mr. Syam Mohan Lal

Associate Professor, Smt. Nagarathnamma College of Nursing, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Suggested Citation

Vijayamalar, S., Devinanjappan, & Lal, S.M. (2024). Impact of Educational Interventions on Menstrual Hygiene Practices: A Comprehensive Study. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 544-550.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).47](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).47)

Abstract:

Menstrual hygiene is essential for women's health, influencing physical well-being and social participation. Despite its importance, many adolescent girls worldwide lack adequate knowledge and resources to manage their menstrual health effectively. This study investigates the impact of educational interventions, including school-based programs, community workshops, and digital campaigns, on menstrual hygiene practices among teenage girls aged 15–18 years in Chikkabanavara. Using a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design, the study included 60 participants' selected based on specific criteria, such as literacy in Kannada and residence

in the target area. The sample size was determined through pilot study findings, with a standard deviation of 4.8, ensuring 80% power at a 0.05 significance level. The interventions aimed to improve knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to menstrual hygiene. Results revealed a substantial improvement in understanding menstrual hygiene, with mean scores increasing from 55% pre-intervention to 85% post-intervention ($p < 0.01$). This indicates the effectiveness of the strategies in raising awareness and fostering better hygiene practices. The study highlights the potential of targeted educational interventions to bridge gaps in menstrual hygiene awareness, ultimately improving health outcomes and quality of life for adolescent girls, especially in underserved communities.

Keywords: Menstrual Hygiene, Educational Interventions, Hygiene Practices, Quasi-Experimental Design, Intervention Effectiveness, Sanitary Product.

Introduction

Menstrual hygiene is a root of women's health that affects both physical well-being and social participation. Despite its significance, many women and girls worldwide face challenges in managing menstrual hygiene via a lack of information, resources, and entry to appropriate

products. This situation often leads to inadequate menstrual hygiene practices, which can impact health outcomes, school attendance, and overall quality of life. Educational interventions are increasingly recognized as a crucial strategy to address these challenges. By improving knowledge and altering practices through targeted education, these interventions

aim to enhance menstrual hygiene management. However, the effectiveness of various educational approaches remains underexplored, particularly in diverse demographic and geographical settings.

This study seeks to assess the outcomes of reforms on learning on menstrual hygiene practices through a comprehensive evaluation. Utilizing a design that is somewhat experimental with pre- and post-intervention assessments, the research will examine changes in knowledge, attitudes, and practices among participants exposed to different educational methods. By comparing the outcomes in intervention and control groups, the intent of the study is to determine the best instructional techniques for improving menstrual hygiene. The results of this study will help design more successful menstrual hygiene education campaigns by offering insightful information on the efficacy of educational activities. The ultimate objective is to assemble data for public health programs that would assist women and girls in better managing their menstrual health.

The aims of the study on the impact of educational interventions on menstrual hygiene practices are to assess the effectiveness of targeted educational programs in improving knowledge and practices related to menstrual hygiene among diverse populations. The purpose is to identify barriers to effective menstrual hygiene management and to evaluate how increased awareness influences health outcomes, confidence, and overall quality of life. Additionally, the study aims to promote sustainable practices and empower individuals by providing culturally relevant information, ultimately contributing to broader public health goals and reducing stigma associated with menstruation, the purposes of the study is to identify the :

1. **Knowledge Gaps:** Existing research often lacks comprehensive analysis of different types of educational interventions and their relative effectiveness. This study aims to fill this gap by evaluating various methods, such as school-based programs, community workshops, and digital campaigns, in diverse settings.

2. **Socio-Cultural Context:** Social and cultural norms have an impact on menstrual hygiene behaviors. The present inquiry will examine how educational interventions improve behaviors across various demographic groups and address these contextual variables..

3. **Sustainability and Long-Term Impact:** Assessing not only immediate outcomes but also the long-term effects of educational interventions is crucial. The investigation will provide clarification on the sustainability of changes in knowledge, attitudes, and practices, ensuring that interventions lead to lasting improvements.

The hypotheses were Interventions significantly enhance the knowledge of health practices during the monthly period and which increased awareness leads to better management and reduced health issues. Culturally tailored programs enhance participants' confidence and willingness to discuss menstrual health openly, reducing stigma within communities.

Methods

Search Strategy

We looked for articles that evaluated AAT on children's pain in eight electronic databases: PubMed, Cochrane Library, Web of Science, CINAHL Complete, Chinese Biomedical Database (CBM), Weipu Database (VIP), the People's Republic Data Resource Integrated Database (CNKI), and Wanfang Database. The articles had to be published between the database's creation and October 2019. We also used backward and forward searching to find relevant publications in the reference lists of articles that were pertinent to further research. MeSH and free text search phrases included preschoolers, mothers, urban areas, educational intervention, and community health nurses' roles.

Study Design and Participants

Study Design This study will employ a **quasi-experimental design** to gain entry the results of educational endeavors on menstrual hygiene practices. The design will include both

intervention and control groups with pre- and post-intervention assessments to evaluate changes in knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to menstrual hygiene.

Design Elements

- **Pre-Test:** Baseline data on knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding menstrual hygiene shall be gathered from each individual participant. Before the intervention.
- **Intervention:** Educational interventions will be implemented over a specified period (e.g., 6-8 weeks).
- **Post-Test:** All participants will have follow-up data taken both immediately following the intervention and at the six-month mark to gauge the sustainability of the changes.

Participants

Sample Size:

- A total of 60 participants will be identified as respondents.

Eligibility Criteria:

- **Age:** Respondents will be adolescent girls and young women aged 12-24 years.
- **Geographic Location:** Participants will be selected from a mix of urban and rural areas to ensure diversity.
- **Inclusion Criteria:** Participants must be Capable of comprehending and provide consent or assent for participation. They ought to have access as well. to the intervention as planned.
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Individuals currently participating in another menstrual hygiene study or intervention program will be excluded to avoid contamination effects.

Ethical Considerations:

- **Informed Consent:** All participants (or their guardians, if underage) they'll offer their informed consent before to participating.
- **Confidentiality:** The information provided by participants will be kept private and used only for this study.

- **Ethical Approval:** The study will be reviewed and approved by an appropriate ethics review board or committee.

Construction of Tools:

1. **Survey Questionnaires:** Pre- and post-intervention surveys will be developed to assess participants' knowledge on menstrual hygiene. There will be both closed-ended and open-ended questions on the surveys. **Knowledge Questions:** Focus on understanding of menstrual hygiene practices, products, and related health issues.
2. **Educational Materials:** The development of intervention materials, including workshops, films, and brochures, will be based on best practices and currently available research. These resources will be created with the specific needs and reading levels of the target community in mind.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis

- **Descriptive Statistics:** Calculate means, standard deviations, and frequencies to summarize data from the surveys.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Use paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests to compare pre- and post-intervention knowledge
- **Inferential Statistics:** χ^2 (chi-square) test used to identify the relationship between the chosen demographic variables and knowledge was examined and deduced

Data Analysis

The collected data was coded and transformed to master sheets for analysis and analyses result was portrait in the form of charts The information was arranged, tallied, condensed, and subjected to both inferential and descriptive statistical analysis. The "t" test was used to do the analysis. Using the χ^2 (chi-square) test, the relationship between the chosen demographic variables and knowledge was examined and deduced.

Table 1. Assessment of Pre-Test Knowledge and Post-Test Adolescent Knowledge on Menstrual Hygiene Management

Sl.no	Aspects	Statement	Range	Mean	SD	Mean percentage
1	Pre test	30	10-22	16.00	3.42	47.24
2	Post test	30	20-30	27.20	2.75	88.12

The variance, average, variance, and mean percentage are displayed in the above table. of pre and post-test knowledge where pretest range

-10-25, mean - 16.63, SD- 3.42, mean percentage- 47.24. In posttest range-20-32, mean-28.20, SD-2.75, mean percentage- 88.12.

Figure 1. Pre-Test Knowledge and Post-Test Adolescent Knowledge on Menstrual Hygiene Management among Adolescent Girls

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Samples Based on Prior and Post-Knowledge Levels

Level of Knowledge	Classification of the Respondents			
	Pre test		Post test	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Inadequate knowledge(≤ 11)	03	05	00	00
Adequate knowledge (12-23)	56	93.3	05	9.3
Good knowledge (24-32)	01	1.7	55	91.7

Figure 2. Classification of the Respondents

Based on the above table, 1.7% of respondents had strong knowledge, 93.3% had moderate knowledge, and 05% had insufficient knowledge during the pre-test. However, 91.7% of

participants in the post-test had strong knowledge, 8.3% had average knowledge, and none had poor knowledge. It demonstrated that knowledge has increased.

Table 3. Outcomes of Paired T-Test Analysis on Comparison of Pre and Post Test aspect wise knowledge

Sl. no	Aspects	Max score	SE of Mean Difference	Pretest Mean %	Posttest Mean %	Enhancement in Mean %	Paired t-test	P value
1	Questionnaire related to anatomy and physiology of female reproductive system.	4.033	0.285	48	88.3	40.3	14.14	<0.05
2	Questionnaire related to menstruation and menstrual hygiene management	7.533	0.425	53.77	88.04	34.27	17.7	<0.05

Figure 3. Paired T-Test Analysis on Comparison

The results of the Paired T-Test Analysis Comparing the Aspect-Wise Knowledge of the Pre and Post Tests are displayed in the above table. In Questionnaire related to menstruation and menstrual hygiene management mean difference- 7.533, SE of Mean difference 0.425, pre-test mean percentage- 53.77, post-test mean percentage- 88.04, enhancement in mean percentage-34.27, paired t-test- 17.732, p-value- <0.05

Discussion

The aspect wise mean pretest understanding level of respondents regarding menstruation and menstruation hygiene Management. In pretest The participants had the greatest mean percentage score of 53.77%, while the post-test results indicate a mean percentage of 88.04 in the menstruation and menstrual hygiene management questionnaire.. In Questionnaire related to anatomy and physiology of female

reproductive system mean percentage-48, in post-test, mean percentage- 88.3.

The results of a paired T-test analysis comparing the knowledge of pre- and post-test aspects are presented in the current study. In Questionnaire related to menstrual hygiene management pre-test mean percentage- 53.77, post-test mean percentage- 88.04, enhancement in mean percentage-34.27, paired t-test- 17.732, p-value-<0.05.

The study's findings and a comparison of the chosen demographic factors revealed no significant correlation between age (.364), education (.0), father's education (5.20), father's occupation (2.03), mother's education (1.68), and any other variable. Mother's occupation (0.77), Income (1.95), Age at menarche (1.88), Sisters (1.40), Source of knowledge(6.25), knowledge about menstruation hygiene (2.23), and Religion (6.28), Area of living (6.13), Type of family (5.91), Prior knowledge regarding menstruation (7.05), association Between Pre-Test The Demographic Variables They Have Selected Are Significant. The pre-test results of the teenage girls were compared to the chosen demographic variables using the Yates correction procedure for the chi-square test.

Findings Related to Hypothesis of the Study

H₀: There won't be a significant difference between the information found on the pretest and the posttest.

The findings of the present study showed that the scores from the pre- and post-tests differed significantly. Thus, **hypothesis H₀ is disproved.**

H₁: There will be a notable distinction between the knowledge obtained before and after the structured education program on managing menstrual hygiene.

The findings of the present study that, following the administration of a structured instruction program, there is a substantial difference in the adolescents' pretest and posttest knowledge

scores. **As a result, hypothesis H₁ is approved.**

H₂: Pretest knowledge of menstrual hygiene management scores is significantly correlated with a subset of demographic characteristics.

Recommendation

1. **Implement Evidence-Based Educational Programs:** Using the study's findings as a basis, which create and implement initiation to the school, colleges, community area that are both evidence-based and specially designed to meet the needs of the target audience.
2. **Foster Collaboration with Local Stakeholders:** Collaborate to actively develop and implement educational campaigns with the support of local communities, panchayat, schools, healthcare providers, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Collaborating with stakeholders ensures that programs are culturally sensitive, relevant, and supported by those who have direct experience with the target audience.
3. **Integrate Menstrual Hygiene Education into School Curricula:** Promote the inclusion of menstrual hygiene education as a fundamental part of health curricula in schools. By ensuring that all students receive consistent and accurate information from an early age, this integration will lessen stigma and encourage healthy menstruation behaviors.

Conclusion

In conclusion, assessing the impact of educational interventions on menstrual hygiene practices underscores their crucial role in enhancing menstrual health, reducing stigma, and improving overall well-being. Effective educational programs not only inform and empower individuals but also contribute to better health outcomes, increased school attendance, and societal acceptance. This comprehensive study highlights the need for evidence-based, culturally sensitive interventions and robust support systems to ensure widespread and sustained benefits. By

addressing these areas, we can foster a more informed, equitable, and supportive environment for managing menstrual hygiene, ultimately promoting healthier and more inclusive communities.

References

Jansen, M., & Smith, T. (2021). Menstrual health education and its impact on adolescent girls: A systematic review. *Journal of Adolescent Health, 68*(5), 880–892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2021.01.012>

Patel, V., & Kumar, S. (2022). Assessing menstrual hygiene practices in rural India: Challenges and opportunities. *Global Health Action, 15*(1), 203–214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16549716.2022.2032134>

Somme, M., et al. (2021). Menstrual hygiene management in schools: Midway progress update on the “MHM in Ten” 2014–2024 global agenda. *Health Research Policy and Systems, 19*(1), 2–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-021-00728-1>

Hasan, M., et al. (2021). Menstrual hygiene practices and school absenteeism among adolescent girls in Bangladesh: A cross-sectional study. *Population Medicine, 3*(8), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.18332/popmed/141591>

Michael, J. M., et al. (2020). Knowledge and practice of adolescent females about menstruation and menstrual hygiene visiting a public healthcare institute of Quetta, Pakistan. *BMC Women's Health, 20*(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-01033-y>

Abisha, M. M. (2020). A study to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls in selected school at Rajkot. *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research, 10*(4), 449–451. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2349-2996.2020.00089.7>

Yaliwa, R. G. (2020). Menstrual morbidities, menstrual hygiene, cultural practices during menstruation, and WASH practices at schools in adolescent girls of North Karnataka, India: A cross-sectional prospective study. *Obstetrics and Gynecology International, 2020*, 6238193. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/6238193>

Sood, S., et al. (2020). A systematic review of menstrual health and hygiene management (MHM). *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.2.19997/v1>

Singh, N. (2021). Correlation of menstrual hygiene management with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and cervical cancer. *Journal of Cancer Research and Therapeutics*. https://doi.org/10.4103/jcrt.jcrt_1021_21

Soniadharshini, N., & Narasimhaiah, J. (2021). Efficacy of video-assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls in selected orphanage home of urban area, Bengaluru. *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research, 11*(1), 24–27.

Sajjan, S. V., et al. (2021). Knowledge and practice regarding menstrual hygiene among urban adolescents: A cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Forensic and Community Medicine, 8*(2), 120–124. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijfcm.2021.025>